

Review of the Regulatory Environment Governing Stablecoins in Singapore and the Implications of Contemporary Legislative Evolution in Competing Jurisdiction

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Abstract- Technological evolution enabling the offering of digital assets, particularly, using crypto technology and distributed ledger technology, have made various crypto assets viable. However, with the perception of high risks and threats posed by crypto assets, most markets around the world are yet to legalize the circulation of crypto currencies or offering of other digital assets. Even in jurisdictions that have not strictly banned crypto assets or currencies, relevant regulatory standards to enhance the legal environment governing digital assets are rare to come. However, with the efforts of pertinent international institutions, regulatory emergence could be noticed, especially in prominent financial markets like Singapore, Hong Kong and USA. The pioneering regulation in this regard are seen first in one low-risk crypto asset offerings namely the stablecoins. The present paper aims at assessing the regulatory developments governing stablecoins in Singapore as one of the first jurisdictions to introduce an exclusive stablecoins regulatory regime and assess its relative strength and potential limitations from the perspective of stablecoins business operators. The paper also aims to undertake an assessment of contemporary regulatory development in two competing jurisdictions of Hong Kong and USA that have introduced the latest legislative instruments comprehensively governing stablecoins. Three distinct parts of the paper carryout a close analysis of a selected set of regulatory standards and related developments in the three jurisdictions with some relevant references to the international regulatory efforts. The paper concludes with an analysis of the major findings relating to the regulatory standards in Singapore and certain comparative regulatory features to derive relevant implications and recommendations.

Keywords- Crypto and Distributed Ledger Technology, Digital Assets, Stablecoins, Singapore, Comparative Regulation, Hong Kong and USA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Prominent jurisdictions like London, New York, Hong Kong, and Singapore constantly strive to usurp the position of the 'top financial centre' in the world, as well as in the region, by assiduously enhancing their respective financial market conditions and regulatory environment. With the persistent efforts

in both aspects, their rankings shift periodically. As highlighted by some surveys, while Singapore previously enjoyed the top position in Asia, Hong Kong regained the position in September 2024 along with recognition of the third top financial centre in the world, ranked right after New York and London. Although the choice of markets to enter, invest and operate in goods or services could be determined by business entities primarily based on various

economic factors or market size, legal factors and regulatory conditions play an indispensable role in many sectors. Financial services market is one of those sectors, where congenial legal environment will certainly weigh in while choosing the markets. The legal factors that influence the choice of markets in financial industry will range from broad elements like the existence of rule of law, nature of the legal system, or scope of binding international obligations, and specific set of regulatory standards governing a particular sector or segments of the market. In terms of broad-based legal elements, Hong Kong and Singapore are highly regarded for upholding rule of law in the respective jurisdictions and have a same type of legal system belonging to the common law family.

Regarding international obligations, one of the pertinent fields of comparison will be the respective undertakings of both jurisdictions regarding market access commitments under the General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS) of the World Trade Organization (WTO). A review of their undertakings in the financial sector specific commitments under the GATS Schedule reveals that both jurisdictions provide market access for foreign entities to have commercial presence albeit with different levels of restrictions. A comparison of the limitations on market access and related restrictions imposed by both jurisdictions regarding commercial presence in the pertinent sectors like 'banking and other financial services' and in subsectors like 'payment and money transmission services' reveals that the number of specific restrictions imposed by Singapore have been generally higher than Hong Kong. For example, Hong Kong imposed no restrictions on commercial presence in the subsector of 'payment and money transmission services' under the original schedule of commitments dated 15th April 1994. However, on the same subsector, Singapore imposed several restrictions on commercial presence under its original schedule of commitments dated 15th April 1994. Moreover, over the years, the number of times, the specific commitments in financial services were replaced with newer ones has been more in case of Singapore.

In case of Hong Kong, it replaced its Financial

Services Section relating to the Schedule of Specific Commitments under the GATS twice since the original Schedule of Specific Commitments was deposited on 15th April 1994. However, in comparison, Singapore has replaced its Financial Services Section relating to the Schedule of Specific Commitments under the GATS a greater number of times since its original Schedule of Specific Commitments was deposited on 15th April 1994. However, despite such difference, market access for foreign financial service providers both in Hong Kong and Singapore are relatively more liberalized than other markets in the region which plays an important role in establishing their positions as top two financial centres in Asia for a long time. However, what distinguishes them from each other and their continuous efforts to be on the very top, calls for a closer scrutiny and assessment of any specific efforts they undertake to excel in different market segment and services in the financial sector. In this regard, some of the prominent fields on which both jurisdictions made extensive efforts includes assimilation of fintech and digitalization of financial products and services. The objective of the present paper is to identify and assess some of the conspicuous regulatory efforts made in Singapore on the latter field, especially in promoting stablecoins market and determine whether it calls for any revitalization in the light of the recent legislative development in the competing jurisdictions like Hong Kong and the US.

The motivation for the choice of stablecoins for the study is due a major regulatory development in Hong Kong, which in May 2025 passed a Stablecoins Bill, which is destined to enter into force into legal force in August 2025 (Stablecoins Ordinance 2025). This is particularly significant because Hong Kong had been lagging in legalizing and regulating stablecoins in comparison with Singapore, which released its regulatory standards governing stablecoins nearly two years ago in 2023. Despite being late, Hong Kong has adopted a very comprehensive regulatory framework through a detailed legislation and is contemporary to the US enactment on the same subject matter, namely the GENIUS Act 2025 that was also passed and signed in July 2025. Moreover, as Singapore's choice of

governing stablecoins is distinct from Hong Kong, as it mainly used the approach of providing some regulatory clarifications in response to the public consultation on the subject matter and introducing some amendments to pertinent legislation that already existed. A close assessment of the regulatory framework governing stablecoins in Singapore is carried out in this paper, with an aim to discern its strength and weakness in enhancing the legal environment and the attractiveness for stablecoins investors and operators. In the light of the findings, the paper will end with an analysis of major legislative development in Hong Kong and US to determine whether such developments call for a revival of the stablecoins regulatory framework in Singapore to stay on the top of the game.

II. INTROSPECTION OF THE STABLE COINS REGULATORY MEASURES IN SINGAPORE

Singapore initiated a regulatory proposal on stablecoins related activities through a public consultation paper issued by the Monetary Authority of Singapore (MAS) in October 2022 (MAS, 2022). Subsequently, the MAS issued its finalised regulatory approach to stablecoins in August 2023 by issuing a paper setting out its response to the feedback received through the public consultation, which remains as Singapore's main regulatory framework governing stablecoins (MAS, 2023). Comparatively, however, Hong Kong carried out similar public consultation and provided related response earlier than Singapore during January 2022 and January 2023 respectively. The Hong Kong Monetary Authority (HKMA) issued a discussion paper on stablecoins (HKMA, 2022) and the conclusions on that discussion paper (HKMA 2023), which just clarified the regulatory direction Hong Kong would take in governing stable coins. After that clarification, in December 2023, the Financial Services and the Treasury Bureau (FSTB) of Hong Kong along with HKMA issued a legislative proposal to implement the regulatory regime and sought public consultation (FSTB-HKMA 2023).

In the following year in July 2024, the conclusions relating to the proposal to introduce an exclusive legislation governing stablecoins in Hong Kong were issued (FSTB-HKMA 2024). These continued efforts ultimately culminated in the enactment of the Stablecoins Bill, which was passed in May 2025 and will enter into force as a law in August 2025 (HK Stablecoins Ordinance 2025). The sustained efforts of Hong Kong developing regulatory standards and providing a comprehensive regulatory framework through a single legislation should provide Hong Kong an edge in offering a clear and certain legal environment for stablecoin operations. Singapore, on the other hand has chosen to regulate stable coin activities using a piece meal approach, whereby only the activity of issuing a prescribed type of stablecoins (MAS-regulated SCS) in Singapore is regulated through the regulatory standards enumerated in the MAS regulatory response paper 2023 (MAS RRP 2023). Whereas issuance of other types of stable coins or any services or activity (other than issuance) related to the MAS-regulated SCS are treated as digital payment tokens (DPT) and are subjected to a general older legislation namely the Payment Services Act of 2019 (PSA 2029). These divergent approach of Hong Kong and Singapore in regulating stablecoins calls for a close analysis of specific regulatory standards governing stablecoins in both jurisdictions to determine their respective strength and weaknesses.

MAS RRP 2023, at the very outset declares that responses made in that paper will serve as the finalized regulatory approach of stablecoins in Singapore and enumerates the key requirements of the regulatory framework in a separate Annex to the paper. A close review of the relevant requirements and regulatory standards prescribed by the MAS RRP 2023 will help assess the nature of the stablecoins regime in Singapore. Firstly, the MAS RRP 2023 confirmed that only stablecoins that satisfy two specific conditions will be brought with the regulatory scope namely a) to maintain stability, the stable coins should be referenced to the Singapore dollar or a group of ten different currencies (G10 currencies) as the underlying asset (called as the Single Currency Stablecoins or SCS) and b) those coins should have been issued in Singapore.

However, the MAS RRP 2023 clarified that there will be no prohibition for other types of stablecoins to be issued, used or circulated inside Singapore, albeit the fact that they will be treated as DPTs and subjected to the PSA 2019. Similarly, any SCS that are issued outside Singapore and any foreign stablecoins referenced to other currencies or types of assets will not be prohibited in Singapore and will also be subjected to the PSA 2019 as DPTs. This clearly confirms that the specific stablecoins regulatory standards prescribed in MAS RRP 2023 will only govern the SCS issued in Singapore.

In addition, the MAS RRP 2023 confirmed that the Singapore PSA will be extended to govern a new type of payment service called 'Stablecoin Issuance Service' (SIS) to regulate various activities undertaken by a stablecoin issuer. Such regulated activities could also include services related to SCS, like providing their custody and managing their backup reserve assets. The SAS issuers in Singapore are categorized into two major categories and related subcategories. The two categories are 'SCS issued by non-banking entities' and 'SCS issued by banking entities'. The former is subdivided into 'small nonbanking issuers' (with total value of SCS not exceeding 5 million dollars) and 'large nonbanking issuers' (exceeding the 5 million dollars). The small nonbanking issuers will not be generally governed by the requirements of the SCS framework and hence the SCS they issue will be not be classified or recognized as the SCS regulated under the SCS framework (as the small issuers are not required to follow the requirements aimed at maintaining a stable value of the SCS issued).

The stablecoins issuers that fall within the SCS framework are permitted use the term 'MAS-regulated stablecoin', and other DPT service providers and persons not governed by SCS framework are not permitted to use that term. However, this does not mean that such small nonbanking issuers cannot strive to bring their SCS within the category of those being regulated under the SCS framework. If such small issuers intend or anticipate their SCS to exceed the threshold of 5 million in the future, they are permitted to apply for a Major Payment Institution (MPI) license and upon

compliance with the requirements of the SCS framework, would be eligible to be classified as SCS regulated under the SCS framework.

Regarding the SCS issued by banking institutions, the MAS RRP 2023 clarifies that at the beginning of the regime, the tokenized bank liabilities of the SCS issuing banks will not be governed within the SCS framework albeit the possibility that they could be brought within the purview of the framework in the future. In addition, the future possibility to recognize other bank issued tokens (that meet the required standards) as stablecoins under the SCS framework was also recognized. The SCS framework enumerated by the MAS RRP 2023 imposes three major sets of requirements on the issuers of MAS regulated SCS namely a) requirements pertaining to reserve assets, b) requirements relating to redemption and, c) requirements limiting SCS sought to be issued in multiple jurisdictions. Among these, the reserve asset requirements are the most elaborate due to the significant role they plan in ensuring the fundamental quality of stability.

In relation to the first set of requirements on the issuers of MAS, there are four specific prescriptions related to the reserve assets. The first specific prescription relates to the composition of the reserve assets, whereby the relevant SCS issuers are mandated to maintain reserve assets that are low risk in nature. Moreover, they should maintain a risk management policy that is robust and resilient to tackle various types of potential risks like credit risk, and liquidity risks. In addition, they are obliged to demonstrate to the regulator the reserve buffers are at sufficient levels in par with the outstanding SCS that are in circulation. Under the second specific prescription, the relevant SCS issuers are required to segregate the reserve assets and hold them separately from other assets they hold that are not part of the reserve assets. To achieve the segregation, those reserve assets should be held in licensed financial institutions providing custodial services in Singapore or by custodians abroad having a minimum credit rating of A- and have a branch in Singapore that is regulated by MAS and is licensed to provide custodial services.

Under the third specific prescription, the SCS framework recognizes the need for a range auditing and reporting requirements related to the reserve assets, to achieve a high level of transparency related to the backing and enhance the trust in the underlying value of the SCS. Finally, through the fourth specific prescription, the SCS framework imposes three kinds of prudential requirements on the SCS issuers, namely a) a high level of base capital to ensure that there is sufficient financial commitment to sustain the SCS business for a long period, b) sufficient level of liquid assets to support recovery or orderly winding-down and independent annual auditing to ensure the maintenance of appropriate level of those assets, and c) requirements prohibiting the SCS issuers from undertaking activities or business offerings like lending, dealing or fund management related services that could pose risks to the fundamental activity of issuing SCS.

In relation to the second set of requirements pertaining to redemption, the issuers of SCS issuers are obliged to redeem the par value of any SCS to the users within five business days in situations where users directly redeem with the issuers. Regarding the third set of requirements limiting the SCS sought to be issued in multiple jurisdictions, the MAS RRP 2023 confirms that the regulator will not permit the issuing of SCS in multiple jurisdictions. This limit is imposed by the MAS due to the perceived difficulties in tracking and verifying issuers' compliance with the regulatory standards in more than one jurisdiction and ensure the sustenance of stability of the related SCS. Therefore, the foreign issuers intending to seek recognition for their SCS in Singapore as the MAS regulated stablecoin should issue their stablecoin solely in a jurisdiction out of Singapore.

The MAS RRP 2023 also indicates that the DPT service providers are permitted a duration of maximum three business days to transmit the regulated SCS to a payee once the transfer is initiated by a payer. The SCS intermediaries are imposed with certain obligations of segregation of assets like, for example, an obligation to segregate the intermediaries' own assets from the MAS

regulated SCS of the customers to reduce risks of any potential misuse of the SCS of the customers. One of the limitations of the MAS RRP 2023 is the lack of any specific requirements regulating systemic stablecoin arrangements (that could potentially have systemic effects), which was put off for future regulatory developments. Finally, the MAS RRP 2023 provided certain key clarifications on some specific regulatory standards. It clarified that MAS-regulated SCS will not be treated as deposits and hence will not benefit from the protection offered by the Deposit Insurance Scheme. It also emphasized that regular monitoring of the development of stablecoins market is crucial to address concerns relating to their implications on the overall monetary sovereignty and financial stability and to introduce required safeguard measures to preserve the efficiency of monetary policy and the stability of the financial system of Singapore.

III. REVIEW OF CERTAIN REGULATORY FEATURES IN HONG KONG STABLECOINS ORDINANCE 2025

Hong Kong's policy debates surrounding stablecoins were influenced by some of the international regulatory standard recommendations made by pertinent international institutions like the Financial Stability Board (FSB). The FSB being one of the pioneering bodies prescribing national regulatory standards for the governance of crypto assets including stable coins issued High Level Recommendations on global stable coin arrangements (FSBHLR 2020 and 2023) in 2020 and followed by a revised set of recommendations in 2023. Similarly the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS) of the Bank of International Settlement (BIS) issued prudential regulatory standards governing crypto asset operations carried out by the banks (BCBS, 2022). Similarly, the Committee on Payment and Market Infrastructure (CPMI) along with the International Organization of Securities Commissions (IOSCO) prescribed the principles of financial market infrastructure that should be applied for stablecoin arrangements in national markets. (CPMI-IOSCO, 2022). Other prominent institutions like International Monetary Fund have also issued general guidance relating to

crypto asset markets involving stablecoins. (Parma Bains and others, 2022). During this period of international developments, the Hong Kong Monetary Authority (HKMA) initiated its first major domestic effort in 2022 by issuing a Stablecoin Discussion Paper (HKSDP 2022). A quick review of the HKSDP 2022 clearly indicates that Hong Kong made clear choice to prioritize the development of a regulatory framework governing stablecoins as the first focus among several crypto assets.

The HKMA was fully convinced of the growing importance of stablecoins and the need for its regulation. The emphasis of HKMA was driven by its conviction about the role stablecoins will play in the future as a means of payment and the consequential significance it will gain in the financial system. Therefore, to be well prepared to address any impact stable coins could cause on monetary and financial systems, HKMA initiated regulatory action. Through the paper, public consultation was sought in Hong Kong and based on the feedback received key conclusions were made in 2023 identifying the parameters of the regulatory direction (HKMA 2023). However, unlike Singapore, which also carried out similar regulatory consultation and related conclusions during the same year, Hong Kong limit itself in prescribing the regulatory standards through the conclusions paper. It immediately followed up with a legislative proposal to implement the proposed regulations on stablecoin (FSTB and HKMA, 2023). Development of a new licensing regime for issuing fiat referenced stablecoins (FRS) through an exclusive legislative instrument was chosen as the means to attain regulatory goals. After the legislative proposal in 2023, Hong Kong SAR prepared and passed a Bill governing stablecoins on 21 May 2025, which is then scheduled to enter into force as the Stablecoins Ordinance 2025 in August 2025. A selective review of some of its regulatory features will provide certain comparative insights for Singapore to determine if any major distinctions and gaps have emerged and whether there is a need to revitalise the regulatory framework in Singapore.

The Hong Kong Ordinance creates a comprehensive legal framework which systematically prescribes regulatory standards governing a range of matters

pertinent to licensing of stablecoins issuance and other related activities, functions and powers of regulatory authorities, offences and related sanctions, and mechanism to seek review of certain decisions and avenues for judicial appeal. It also imposes a duty of confidentiality and regulates various fundamental issues using separate systematic schedule. There are eight schedules prescribed under the Ordinance that deal with a set of specified stablecoin affairs, minimum criteria and prescribed fees for seeking a license, and grounds of revocation of a stablecoins license. There is a schedule that addresses matters of internal governance of the stablecoins business by prescribing the powers of a statutory manager appointed by a licensee. The Ordinance establishes a stablecoin review tribunal and a separate schedule prescribes its administration and functions. Finally, while prescribing pertinent transitional provisions to implement the legislation smoothly, the Ordinance also identifies potential amendments needed for other legislation in the light of the introduction of the new regulatory system.

The nature of the 'stablecoin' is defined under the Ordinance comprehending the broad characteristics inspired by international recommendations as well as a set of exclusions enumerating certain digital representation of values that will not constitute a stable coin. The Ordinance further defines the term 'specified stablecoin' that will fall within the purview of regulation under the legislation. Specified stablecoin is defined to include a concrete set of characteristics that should be satisfied, followed by an enabling provision whereby HKMA is conferred with the powers to prescribe new characteristics and asset bases in the future for bringing them within the regulatory scope of the new regime. The Ordinance also defines pertinent terms like 'licensed stable coin', 'offering specific stablecoin' and 'regulated stablecoin activity' with specific connotations, which enables the regulator to categorically distinguish and govern variations in types of stablecoins and stablecoin activities. This makes the regulatory framework emerging from the Ordinance much more vibrant and inherently capable of addressing the constant flux in the developments in digital, crypto and distributed ledger technologies.

The regulations of 'specified stablecoins' are prescribed in two major categories, with the first one imposing various restriction on a range of activities related to specified stablecoins. This is followed by the introduction of a very elaborate 'licensing regime'. The licensing regime prescribes the licensing process and the related governing conditions. Provisions governing the ownership and management of licensee are some of the important prescriptions governing controller and management of the licensee. Finally, the licensing regime confers various powers upon the regulatory authority for the purpose of management and control of the licensee. The licensing regime under the Ordinance in the beginning is confined to the specified stablecoins which are fiat referenced involving one or more official currencies and no other asset bases. However, with the possibility to expand the asset bases of the specified stablecoins in the future, any concerns of limited scope of the stablecoins issuance permitted in Hong Kong should dwindle. The major activities that mandate license under the new stablecoins regime in Hong Kong could be encapsulated into distinct categories. The foremost 'regulated stablecoin activity' is the act of issuance of specified stablecoins in Hong Kong, followed by the category of specified stablecoins issued outside Hong Kong, which are however referenced to Hong Kong dollar fully or partially to achieve their required stability. The final category encompasses activities that could potentially be specified by HKMA as a regulated activity.

For the grant of license, numerous conditions could be imposed at the time of the grant or could be even added subsequently or be subjected to amendments. This approach provides a wide base for the regulator to introduce measures anytime to ensure the stability and sustainability of the specified stablecoins governed under the Ordinance. The conditions contemplated in this regard are a wide variety capable of sustaining and enhancing stability. The conditions could take various forms like business activity restrictions, reserve asset requirements including prescriptions pertaining to the management and use of those assets, demand for maintenance of additional financial resources, demands to cease or continue business activities

that are licensed, and requirements related to the accounts of the licensee and demands of disclosure. It is also important to note that the Ordinance contemplates the possibility of imposition of conditions that could restrict the maximum value of a licensed specified stable coin. Despite these elaborate conditions being imposed by the Ordinance, it provides measures that would guarantee necessary procedural fairness to a licensee. In addition to these general conditions, the Ordinance also mandates various specific 'minimum criteria' a licensee should satisfy, which are prescribed in a separate schedule enclosed to the Ordinance. The minimum criteria enumerated in the schedule reaches all bolts and nuts in the governance of the operations and management of the stablecoin to ensure effective regulatory supervision. But still the new regime could be seen as stringent, although the legislator would seek to justify the range of conditions and the minimum criteria in the light of the underlying risks and vulnerability, the issuance and circulation of stablecoins poses for consumers and the market.

IV. SELECTIVE FEATURES OF THE CONTEMPORARY LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK GOVERNING STABLECOINS IN THE USA

The US Congress passed its Stablecoins Bill in July 2025, which followed by the signature of the US President became a law called the 'Guiding and Establishing National Innovation for U.S. Stablecoins Act' (GENIUS Act 2025). This signifies as a pioneering major US federal legislation governing stablecoins (Rafael Nam, 2025). Moreover, the choice of enactment of the regulatory regime in the form of a comprehensive legislation to govern stablecoins aligns with the regulatory approach of Hong Kong that enacted its Stablecoins Ordinance contemporaneously. However, from a comparative insight, it is evident that US legislation is not as comprehensive as that of the Hong Kong Ordinance. The analysis also reveals that that the provisions of the GENIUS Act assume some distinct characteristics as a federal legislation to deal with various state level

governance and related mechanisms governing stable coins. Moreover, the comparison of the US regime also reveals that there are differences in other substantive standards of regulation, which indicate some specific characteristics of choice of the US regulators made to satisfy the US financial market conditions and policy preferences. At the same time, the comparison also reveals some important homogeneity between the US and Hong Kong regimes. US regime, despite the common prevalence of other types of crypto assets in their markets, have chosen to limit the scope of the regulation under the GENIUS Act mainly to payment related stablecoins as in the case of Hong Kong. Similarities are also visible in other characteristics and legislative patterns like in case of the definitions of the fundamental operative legal terms and principles.

In terms of differences, the US GENIUS Act, unlike Hong Kong mainly defines one generic term referring to the stablecoin namely the 'payment stablecoin'. The definition prescribed it as a digital asset serving as a means of payment or settlement. The definition also qualifies the 'issuer' of the coin as the one representing or creating reasonable expectation of its stable value. The stable value should be relative to a 'monetary value'. It also imposes a categorical obligation relating to the conversion, redemption or repurchase of the issued coin for a fixed amount of 'monetary value'. The term 'monetary value' is defined to include a 'national currency' or a 'deposit' denominated in a national currency. In this context, it is important to note that the possibility of using a 'a deposit' as a reference value in the US law enhances the choices relating to the pegged asset for the issuance of a stablecoin. In this aspect, the parallel provision found in the definition of 'specified stablecoin' in Hong Kong as it stands now only permits stablecoins that are pegged to one or more official currencies. As discussed earlier, even though HKMA could potentially notify in the future expanding the reference assets to 'other units of account' or 'stores of economic value', currently the choice of reference to an underlying asset recognized in the Hong Kong Ordinance will have a narrower scope than in the US.

The US regime while defining the term of payment stablecoin interestingly refers to the broader term namely 'digital asset', which is defined as any digital representation of value recorded using cryptography and distributed ledger technology. Moreover, the definition imposes a restriction that that the digital asset should not be a national currency or a security issued by an investment company. To potentially pave way for future expansion of the regulatory scope to other types of non-payments related stablecoins, the GENIUS Act defines the type of stablecoin called 'endogenously collateralized stablecoins' (ECS). An ECS is defined as a digital asset consisting of a representation provided by its originator with a guarantee of the conversion, redemption or repurchase of the stablecoins for a fixed value. Such a fixed value should be with reference to another digital asset created or maintained by the same originator.

In comparison, choice of Hong Kong Ordinance providing a direct reference and definition of the term 'stablecoin' along with a definition of 'specified stablecoin' to indicate the stablecoins that will fall within the scope of the regime provides a more systematic treatment in prescribing the categories of the stablecoins that are regulated. Moreover, the inclusion of the three separate definitions of other types of stable coins in the Hong Kong Ordinance, namely asset-linked stable coin, global stablecoin and algorithm-based stablecoin, also provides the framework to effectively distinguish potential variations with reference to the underlying assets, geographical reach and technological basis of the stablecoins. The US regime as alluded earlier also defines various terms that are germane to its local conditions and legal system and notable terms in this regard includes 'digital asset service provider', 'Federal qualified payment stablecoin issuer', 'foreign payment stablecoin issuer', 'institution-affiliated party', 'money', 'national currency', 'permitted payment stablecoin issuer', 'person', 'primary federal payment stablecoin regulator', 'stablecoin certification review committee', 'state-chartered depository institution', 'state payment stablecoin regulator', and 'state qualified payment stablecoin issuer'. The nature and scope of definition of these terms indicate various distinct regulatory

characteristics that are unique to the US context, which be assessed by global investors intending to operate in the US market.

A closer examination of some of the above referred terms reveals certain unique characteristics that will a focus of interest. A good example in this regard pertains to the definition of a 'foreign payment stablecoin issuer' who is described as an issuer of a payment stablecoin that is organized under laws of or domiciled in a foreign country or a territory of the US, American Samoa, Guam, Puerto Rico, or the Virgin Islands. However, the GENIUS Act prescribes that such an issuer should not belong to the category of issuers defined as 'permitted payment stablecoin issuer' under the Act. Similarly, the definition of 'federal qualified payment stablecoin issuer', under the Act enlist certain types of entities namely a 'Federal branch' or a 'non-banking entity' (excluding a State qualified payment stablecoin issuer) that have obtained the approval to issue payment stablecoins.

The Act also defines a related category of 'federal qualified nonbank payment stablecoin issuer'. Similarly, another pertinent definition which is relevant to identify the management and personnel of a permitted payment stablecoin issuer is 'institution-affiliated party'. The definition in this regard includes various persons that play the role of a director, controlling stockholder, employee, or officer of a permitted payment stablecoin issuer. Finally, it is also relevant to note that term 'person' is broadly defined to include individual natural persons and specifically enlisted legal persons. The legal persons specifically recognized in this regard are association, company, cooperative organization, corporation, other incorporated or unincorporated business entity, and trust. These distinct characteristics identified from the regulatory prescriptions in the US Act evidences its sophistication in providing a strong set of taxonomy that will certainly facilitate the smooth interpretation and functioning of the related substantive regulatory standards inherent in the US regime.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The review of the stablecoins regulatory regime in Singapore and its salient features reveals various strength and limitations that will influence the choice of Singapore as the regulatory jurisdiction to operate stablecoins issuance and related activities. Moreover, the review of the emerging regulatory environment in the competing jurisdictions of Hong Kong and USA also presents various findings of comparative advantages and disadvantages, which stablecoin business entities will give due regard in choosing the market to invest and operate. As Singapore being one of the earliest jurisdictions to set out its regulatory framework creating necessary regulatory environment for issuance of stablecoins in Singapore, prospective stablecoin businesses will always be keen to assess its essential features and ascertain the regulatory advantages it offers. In this regard, the essential conditions requiring the reference to Singapore dollar or any of the group of ten currencies (G10) under the Singapore regime, could be seen as matching the international and comparative regulatory prescriptions that are aimed at securing stability through high-quality non-volatile assets. However, the limitation of reference to one of the prescribed currencies including within the basket of ten currencies could dissuade some operators interested in issuing stablecoins pegged to currencies out of the prescribed basket or combination of currencies.

In the above context, as revealed by the comparative review in this paper, the other two competing jurisdictions of Hong Kong and USA without such limits could be perceived as more viable jurisdictions providing the required flexibility. In this regard, the new Hong Kong Stablecoins Ordinance is comparatively found to offer much flexibility by the fact that it recognizes the issuance of any fiat referenced stablecoins in Hong Kong or issuance of stable coins outside Hong Kong that are partially or wholly referenced to Hong Kong dollar as well as any fiat referenced stablecoins issued outside Hong Kong and being actively marketed in Hong Kong. Obviously, the range of fiat references or their combinations offered by Hong Kong provides an

important edge over others in attracting stablecoin issuers to Hong Kong.

Moreover, the limit imposed by the Singapore regulatory regime regarding the offering of stablecoins in multiple jurisdictions and mandating foreign issuers to confine to a single jurisdiction out of Singapore could also play out as an inhibiting factor for multinational foreign stablecoin businesses to enter the Singapore market. However, on this aspect, although the regulatory deliberations in Hong Kong and USA did not explicitly debate or consult on the matter, it seems the regulatory position could be the same in all the three regimes. This is mainly due to the language of the relevant definition standards recognizing the situation of foreign issuers primarily with reference to the act of issuing stablecoins in a (singular) jurisdiction outside. However, the actual interpretation by the regulatory authorities may yield a different result in which case, the two jurisdictions could enjoy an advantage over Singapore on the issue in contention.

On the issue of licensing requirement, the bifurcation found in the Singapore regime that mandates relevant license for the issuers of MAS regulated stablecoins with the circulation value exceeding five million Singapore dollars and not bringing the issuers of SCS below that threshold within the regulatory framework on stablecoins could possibly be seen as an advantage by small scale stablecoin operators. However, the new stablecoins legislative framework in Hong Kong and USA not recognizing any such threshold may not be found favourable by such small players. Regarding the reserve asset requirements, the prescription of Singapore emphasizing on low-risk nature of the assets, in comparison with Hong Kong calling for high-quality liquid assets although seem to have a common denominator focusing on the 'quality' of the underlying reserves, could be perceived as posing different onus on the issuers. In Singapore the minimum requirement prescribed that the reserve asset should be at least equivalent to the relevant stablecoins in circulation could be seen as demanding a high level of reserve. However, on this issue, under the circumstances when Hong Kong is yet to prescribe further specific details on the level of reserve assets, it can only be reasonable to assume

that the levels expected will probably not much different.

Another distinct requirement pertaining to issuers' obligation to redeem under the Singapore regime, as identified in the analysis of this paper mandates the redemption of the par value to the users within a period of five days after the demand, could be seen as onerous by prospective issuers in Singapore. However, the absence of demand of redemption within such a short window in the Hong Kong regime could be seen as an advantage. But at the same time, the minimum capital requirements prescribed for establishing stablecoins issuance operations in Singapore will obviously be seen as a comparative advantage over Hong Kong. Finally, on the matter of restrictions imposed upon the issuers of regulated stablecoins pertaining to their freedom to carry out other business activities Singapore regime could be seen as less favourable than Hong Kong. As identified in the paper, this is mainly due to the blanket prohibition Singapore imposes on the SCS issuers from engaging in any other business activities except when they are justifiable as essential and supplementarily to major operations of the regulated SCS in question. Hong Kong regime, on the other hand, recognizing a much wider range of business activities the issuers of specified stablecoins could engage in, albeit subject to the satisfaction of various prescribed conditions and obtaining necessary consent, would be perceived as more attractive for stablecoin business entities intending to diversify beyond a narrow crypto asset market segment.

The above findings and conclusions derived from the assessment and comparative analysis of the selective regulatory features of the Singapore regime governing stablecoins market could be extrapolated with reference to various other specific regulatory standards in Singapore as well as the two other competing jurisdictions studied in this paper. Especially, a much closer comparative analysis of the specific regulatory features emerging in the newly introduced 2025 legislation in the USA will provide distinct and useful insights, being a non-Asian financial market and ranked as the top financial centre in the world. Moreover, much deeper and comprehensive treatment of the subject matter

should be undertaken by future studies, especially using empirical methods, which will no doubt fetch more specific and insightful findings providing meaningful guidance to prospective stablecoin business entities. But from the limited analysis of the regulatory standards undertaken in the present paper, a broad recommendation pertaining to the nature of the Singapore regulatory framework could be proposed.

As evident from the analysis in this paper, the Singapore regulatory standards published in the form of a conclusions paper on the issues arising from a preceding public consultation should be elevated to a formal legislative proposal. Especially, in the light of the fact that two major international financial centres of Hong Kong and USA studied in this paper successfully promulgating an exclusive and comprehensive legislation governing stablecoins certainly makes their domestic regimes much more self-contained and sophisticated. Singapore's regulatory approach to stablecoins could not only be perceived as older but also fragmented due to its approach in regulating related matters using the stablecoins regulatory framework as well as other relatively general legislative instruments like the PSA 2019. The fragmented approach could be seen as inefficient regulation in comparison with the exclusive legislation totally dedicated for the governance of stablecoins in Hong Kong and USA. Moreover, such an approach does not provide the opportunity to consolidate the functioning of the specialist regime through the development of related redressal mechanisms like the stablecoin review tribunal established under the Hong Kong Stablecoins Ordinance 2025. In the light of this recommendation, Singapore should seriously seek the introduction of a legislative proposal for introducing a comprehensive and exclusive legislation to sustain its stablecoins market advantage.

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